

Why Should We Bother to Communicate Astronomy?

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I once attended a lecture on science communication by a prominent BBC radio producer. At the end of the lecture questions were taken by the producer on the ways in which science is communicated in the media and a lively discussion quickly arose. After covering the in and outs of target audiences, pitching articles and news pieces at the right level, the debate settled. Finally one postgraduate promptly raised his hand and proceeded to ask the producer something along the lines of: “*Why should we even bother with science communication?*” He then continued, emotively and quite genuinely, to argue that to try and explain his complex work would simplify it and, ultimately, belittle it. As he went on the room became quieter and quieter.

At the end of the lecture, as I picked up my pen and paper to leave, I tried to understand where my colleague was coming from. As someone who has a passion for communicating science and astronomy to other people I began to question whether I had really taken for granted that mine was a job that needed to be done. Maybe it was because the question was posed without a hint of jest and with complete genuineness that I was jolted. Did my postgraduate colleague have a point — surely not? Was he just being narrow-minded, not seeing the bigger picture and if so how many other scientists shared such a hard-line view? As science communicators these are questions we need to be able to respond to with clarity and strength.

One of the observations which arose in my mind from the lecture hall experience was that here was a young man just starting out in his research career in some field of astronomy; someone of similar age to myself who had grown up in a much more media-orientated world than today’s more experienced researchers. A world where research grants, project funds and big name backing are all linked by the potent ability to communicate, enthuse and convey your own innate passion for your work to someone else. Yet before even starting his career he had already perceived the communication of his work as something that can have a detrimental effect, not a positive one. How so?

It’s no secret that many scientists today feel that communicating their work is not the most important item on their agenda. But neverthe-

less many appreciate its value. Some scientists commendably approach outreach with a passion, whilst others take the view of the postgraduate in the lecture hall. Now this may ultimately depend on the individual’s communication abilities but everyone, communicators and scientists alike, can always improve their skills. It’s the perception within the scientific community of outreach as damaging that we have to shed. If we are to reduce or even reverse this attitude then we must continue to ensure that as science communicators we produce the best work we can.

Our work should maintain credibility at all costs. We should strive to be factually correct whilst conveying the theory, message and science. We should inform not hype, simplify but not patronise and explain without confusion or ambiguity. It’s quite a difficult but — crucially — not an impossible task. These issues have already been widely discussed so I will not explore them much further here. We need simply to make sure that credibility is ingrained in our work so that the interface between scientists and the media is as smooth as possible and is as beneficial to the researcher as it is to us communicators.

The central question is still why we should communicate not how. The discoveries of science and astronomy need to be communicated. Astronomy represents one of the oldest, most captivating sciences there are. Today many laypeople yearn, as they have always done, to understand more about the Universe they live in. As astronomers and scientists we too covet every new major discovery almost with a veneration for progress that has lasted for centuries; it’s our job to disseminate this vital information. I doubt that many people, academic and lay alike, would disagree.

We should communicate astronomy because it is important. It’s important to many people, on a multitude of levels. Take the images from the various space agencies around the world. Millions of people have marvelled at the exquisite detail of the spirals in distant galaxies thanks to the Hubble Space Telescope, or the view of a Saturnian moon they had never even heard of thanks to Cassini. Whilst these images may not be heavily laden with scientific prose, they are incredibly important keys to communicat-

ing the science. If even a small percentage of the millions who see the pictures from space take an interest in what the image actually shows then thousands will be educated in the astronomical workings of the Universe. What would have happened if Vivaldi had decided to show only a few friends the sheet-music to *The Four Seasons* before filing it away? With good communication our lives, our culture and, most importantly for us, our work is so much richer. Astronomy is a stimulating, mystifying, often baffling and immense subject that brings pleasure and intrigue to young and old, experienced and inexperienced all over the world. Not to communicate the wonders of the Universe would be an outrage.

Culturally, the advancement of astronomy has gone hand in hand with the expansion of some of the most vibrant and diverse cultures the world has ever seen. Similarly, those countries which have embraced science throughout history (especially astronomy and space sciences) have also witnessed a growth in the skills of their populace, employment opportunities arise and numerous economic benefits. Without outreach and education few laypeople would know anything about the workings of the Universe, let alone the workings of a research scientist! If we were to stop communicating astronomy how could we ever hope to inspire and bring forward the next generation of astronomers?

In everyday life we communicate because we must do so to survive. It is a central foundation of our human existence; it has been so since our ancestors wandered the dusty plains of Africa. Today, many millennia later, there is absolutely no difference. Astronomy (and science in general) must communicate to survive. If astronomy is to evolve and progress in the burgeoning manner that it has done since it began, then we must not only bother to communicate we must also excel at it.

Bio

Will Gater is a science writer and astronomer based in the UK, currently working for the BBC Sky At Night magazine. His latest popular astronomy book is due to be published in the near future. Visit his website at www.willgater.com.